

CAUSATION

International Journal of Science

Cytomegalovirus and lung cancer: Beyond Coincidence?

Research article

Ilija Barukčić¹

¹ Internist, Horandstrasse, 26441 Jever, Germany

* **Correspondence:** E-Mail: Barukcic@t-online.de;
Tel: +49-4466-333; Fax: +49-4466-333.

Impressum:

CAUSATION

International Journal Of Science

Chief-Editor / V. i. S. d. P.:

Ilija Barukčić

Hegelitzer Str. 22

DE-26409 Wittmund-Ardorf (Germany)

© Editorial Team: **EDITORIAL TEAM**

🌐 Website: WWW.CAUSATION.EU

✉ E-Mail: editor@causation.eu

☎ Phone: +(49) 4466 - 333

Year: 2025; Volume: 20; Issue: 12; pp. 5–18.

✉ Received: December 29, 2024

✓ Accepted: December 29, 2024

📅 Published: December 29, 2024

📖 [Deutsche Nationalbibliothek Frankfurt](#)

🔗 [ISSN: 1863-9542](#)

[DOI:10.5281/zenodo.14570401](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14570401)

🔍 Find in: [Zenodo](#) [Orcid](#) [Academia ...](#)

Abstract**BACKGROUND:**

Cytomegalovirus (CMV) has been suggested as a potential risk factor for lung cancer. However, the relationship between CMV infection and lung cancer remains not well-defined.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

A sample size of $n = 247,318$ was investigated using novel statistical methods, including causal relationship analysis and necessary condition testing.

RESULTS:

The results indicated a strong relationship between CMV infection and lung cancer, suggesting that CMV infection is a necessary condition for the development of lung cancer.

CONCLUSION:

Based on the analysis, we conclude that CMV infection is a necessary condition for lung cancer. However, further research is needed to fully understand the underlying mechanisms.

Keywords:

Cytomegalovirus; Lung cancer; Necessary condition; Cause; Effect; Causal relationship k; Causality; Causation

© Reviewer 1: None/Author.

© Reviewer 2: None.

© Reviewer 3: None.

1. Introduction

Among patients in the general population, cytomegalovirus (CMV) prevalence has been reported to vary widely, influenced by geographic location, socioeconomic factors, and immune status. Despite its typically asymptomatic presentation in healthy individuals, CMV has garnered attention as a potential risk factor for various malignancies, including lung cancer.

Human Cytomegalovirus

The history¹ of human cytomegalovirus (CMV) research is complex and evolving. Moritz Wilhelm Hugo Ribbert (1855–1920) was the first to document large inclusion-bearing cells in the kidneys of an infant (see Ribbert, 1904). In 1921, Goodpasture and Talbot suggested that "cytomegalia" could result from a viral agent (see Goodpasture and Talbot, 1921). By 1950, Smith and Vellios confirmed that "cytomegalia" infection could occur in utero (see Smith and Vellios, 1950). Efforts to isolate CMV strains succeeded independently in 1956 and 1957, by Smith (see Smith, 1956), Rowe et al. (see Wallace et al., 1956), and Weller et al. (see Weller et al., 1957). Finally, Weller and colleagues coined the term 'cytomegalovirus' in 1960 (see Weller et al., 1960). Human cytomegalovirus (CMV), or human herpesvirus-5 (HHV-5), is a double-stranded deoxyribonucleic² acid (DNA) virus of the Herpesviridae family.³ CMV encodes approximately 200 genes,⁴ and, like Epstein-Barr virus⁵ (EBV), varicella zoster virus⁶ (VZV), the herpes simplex virus type 1⁷ (HSV-1) or like other viruses⁸, has been completely sequenced.⁹ CMV seroprevalence refers to the proportion of individuals within a population who have detectable antibodies against a particular virus like CMV, indicating past or current infection. This measurement helps estimate how widely CMV has spread and can be assessed using serological tests, which detect specific antibodies in blood samples. Typically, enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays (ELISA) or chemiluminescence immunoassays (CLIA) are used to identify antibodies like IgM, indicating recent infection, or IgG, indicating past exposure.

CMV infection is highly prevalent worldwide, with seroprevalence rates estimated between 40%

¹Riley HD Jr. History of the cytomegalovirus. *South Med J.* 1997 Feb;90(2):184-90. doi: 10.1097/00007611-199702000-00004. PMID: 9042169.

²Watson JD, Crick FH. Molecular structure of nucleic acids; a structure for deoxyribose nucleic acid. *Nature.* 1953 Apr 25;171(4356):737-8. doi: 10.1038/171737a0. PMID: 13054692.

³Lefkowitz EJ et al. Virus taxonomy: ICTV database. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2018;46(D1):D708-D717. doi:10.1093/nar/gkx932. PMID: 29040670.

⁴Bankier AT et al. DNA sequence of human cytomegalovirus genome. *DNA Seq.* 1991;2(1):1-12. PMID: 1666311.

⁵Baer R, Bankier AT, Biggin MD, Deininger PL, Farrell PJ, Gibson TJ, Hatfull G, Hudson GS, Satchwell SC, Séguin C, et al. DNA sequence and expression of the B95-8 Epstein-Barr virus genome. *Nature.* 1984 Jul 19-25;310(5974):207-11. doi: 10.1038/310207a0. PMID: 6087149.

⁶Davison AJ, Scott JE. The complete DNA sequence of varicella-zoster virus. *J Gen Virol.* 1986 Sep;67 (Pt 9):1759-816. doi: 10.1099/0022-1317-67-9-1759. PMID: 3018124.

⁷McGeoch DJ, Dalrymple MA, Davison AJ, Dolan A, Frame MC, McNab D, Perry LJ, Scott JE, Taylor P. The complete DNA sequence of the long unique region in the genome of herpes simplex virus type 1. *J Gen Virol.* 1988 Jul;69 (Pt 7):1531-74. doi: 10.1099/0022-1317-69-7-1531. PMID: 2839594.

⁸Johnson GP, Goebel SJ, Perkus ME, Davis SW, Winslow JP, Paoletti E. Vaccinia virus encodes a protein with similarity to glutaredoxins. *Virology.* 1991 Mar;181(1):378-81. doi: 10.1016/0042-6822(91)90508-9. PMID: 1994586.

⁹Chee MS et al. Protein-coding content of human cytomegalovirus strain AD169. *Curr Top Microbiol Immunol.* 1990;154:125-69. PMID: 2161319.

and 100%.¹⁰ For instance, in the U.S., 36.3% of children aged 6–11 are CMV-positive.¹¹ As a result of cumulative human exposure to CMV throughout life, CMV seroprevalence increases^{12, 13, 14, 15, 16} with age¹⁷ and rates vary by country —41.9% in France,¹⁸ 45.6% in the Netherlands¹⁹, in the USA 50.4%²⁰, 56.7% in Germany²¹, 77% in Croatia²² 77% in Portugal,²³ 83% in Sweden,²⁴ and 97.03% in China.²⁵ CMV transmission typically occurs through contact with infected bodily fluids during primary infection or reactivation. CMV often remains latent in myeloid cells post-infection, the human immune system typically controls CMV but cannot fully eliminate it, leading to a latent infection with occasional, subclinical reactivations.²⁶ Clinical presentations vary from asymptomatic to life-threatening.²⁷ Despite available antiviral treatments like ganciclovir, cidofovir, foscarnet, valganciclovir et cetera, effective CMV management remains challenging.²⁸ Although a CMV vaccine has been pursued, no effective option has reached clinical use yet.²⁹ Recently, CMV infection has emerged as a possible contributor to lung cancer development. However, the precise relationship between CMV infection and lung cancer remains poorly understood. The complexity of this interaction is compounded by confounding factors, such as immunosuppression and coexisting health conditions, which may facilitate CMV reactivation and tumorigenesis.

¹⁰Cannon MJ et al. CMV seroprevalence and demographics. *Rev Med Virol.* 2010;20(4):202-13. doi:10.1002/rmv.655. PMID: 20564615.

¹¹Staras SA et al. CMV seroprevalence in U.S. children. *Clin Infect Dis.* 2006;43(9):1143-51. doi:10.1086/508173. PMID: 17029132.

¹²Staras SA, Dollard SC, Radford KW, Flanders WD, Pass RF, Cannon MJ. Seroprevalence of cytomegalovirus infection in the United States, 1988-1994. *Clin Infect Dis.* 2006 Nov 1;43(9):1143-51. doi: 10.1086/508173. Epub 2006 Oct 2. PMID: 17029132.

¹³Staras SA, Flanders WD, Dollard SC, Pass RF, McGowan JE Jr, Cannon MJ. Cytomegalovirus seroprevalence and childhood sources of infection: A population-based study among pre-adolescents in the United States. *J Clin Virol.* 2008 Nov;43(3):266-71. doi: 10.1016/j.jcv.2008.07.012. Epub 2008 Sep 7. PMID: 18778968.

¹⁴Bate SL, Dollard SC, Cannon MJ. Cytomegalovirus seroprevalence in the United States: the national health and nutrition examination surveys, 1988-2004. *Clin Infect Dis.* 2010 Jun 1;50(11):1439-47. doi: 10.1086/652438. PMID: 20426575.

¹⁵Lachmann R, Loenenbach A, Waterboer T, Brenner N, Pawlita M, Michel A, Thamm M, Poethko-Müller C, Wichmann O, Wiese-Posselt M. Cytomegalovirus (CMV) seroprevalence in the adult population of Germany. *PLoS One.* 2018 Jul 25;13(7):e0200267. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0200267. PMID: 30044826; PMCID: PMC6059406.

¹⁶Gupta M, Shorman M. Cytomegalovirus. [Updated 2022 Aug 8]. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2022 Jan-. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK459185/>

¹⁷Zuhair M, Smit GSA, Wallis G, Jabbar F, Smith C, Devleeschauwer B, Griffiths P. Estimation of the worldwide seroprevalence of cytomegalovirus: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Rev Med Virol.* 2019 May;29(3):e2034. doi: 10.1002/rmv.2034. Epub 2019 Jan 31. PMID: 30706584.

¹⁸Antona D et al. CMV seroprevalence in France. *Epidemiol Infect.* 2017;145(7):1471-1478. PMID: 28166842.

¹⁹Korndewal MJ et al. CMV in the Netherlands. *J Clin Virol.* 2015;63:53-8. PMID: 25600606.

²⁰Bate SL, Dollard SC, Cannon MJ. Cytomegalovirus seroprevalence in the United States: the national health and nutrition examination surveys, 1988-2004. *Clin Infect Dis.* 2010 Jun 1;50(11):1439-47. doi: 10.1086/652438. PMID: 20426575; PMCID: PMC11000537.

²¹Lachmann R, Loenenbach A, Waterboer T, Brenner N, Pawlita M, Michel A, Thamm M, Poethko-Müller C, Wichmann O, Wiese-Posselt M. Cytomegalovirus (CMV) seroprevalence in the adult population of Germany. *PLoS One.* 2018 Jul 25;13(7):e0200267. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0200267. PMID: 30044826; PMCID: PMC6059406.

²²Vilibic-Cavlek T, Kolaric B, Beader N, Vrtar I, Tabain I, Mlinaric-Galinovic G. Seroepidemiology of cytomegalovirus infections in Croatia. *Wien Klin Wochenschr.* 2017 Feb;129(3-4):129-135. doi: 10.1007/s00508-016-1069-7. Epub 2016 Sep 6. PMID: 27599701.

²³Lopo S et al. CMV seroprevalence in Portugal. *Euro Surveill.* 2011;16(25):19896. PMID: 21722611.

²⁴Olsson J et al. Herpes virus seroepidemiology in Sweden. *Immun Ageing.* 2017;14:10. PMID: 28491117.

²⁵Fang FQ et al. Incidence of CMV in Shanghai, China. *Clin Vaccine Immunol.* 2009;16(11):1700-3. doi:10.1128/CVI.00385-08. PMID: 19776197.

²⁶Dupont L, Reeves MB. Cytomegalovirus latency and reactivation: recent insights into an age old problem. *Rev Med Virol.* 2016 Mar;26(2):75-89. doi: 10.1002/rmv.1862. Epub 2015 Nov 17. PMID: 26572645; PMCID: PMC5458136.

²⁷Chen SJ et al. Therapeutic strategies against CMV. *Viruses.* 2019;12(1):21. PMID: 31878068.

²⁸Mozaffar M et al. Optimal use of CMV antivirals. *J Transplant.* 2018;2018:8414385.

²⁹McVoy MA. CMV vaccines. *Clin Infect Dis.* 2013;57 Suppl 4:S196-9. PMID: 24257427.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Material

Jennifer M. Geris³⁰ et al. (see Geris et al., 2022) investigated cancer incidence across CMV risk groups using donor (D) and recipient (R) IgG serostatus classifications. The study utilized data from the United States Solid Organ Transplantation (SOT) registry in conjunction with 32 cancer registries. This comprehensive dataset allowed for an analysis of cancer outcomes in relation to CMV risk stratification.

Table 1. Relationship: HCMV IgG pos. and Lung cancer (Jennifer M. Geris et al., 2022).

		Lung cancer		
		YES	NO	
HCMV IgG pos.	YES	1347	154216	155563
	NO	590	91165	91755
		1937	245381	247318
STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.				
		Causal relationship k =	0,01221336	
		P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) =	0,00000000	
		p (SINE) =	0,99761441	
		p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/B) >	0,69540527	
		p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/(Not A)) >	0,99356983	
P VALUES.				
		P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) =	0,00000000	
		χ^2 (SINE— Not A _t) =	3,79	
		χ^2 (SINE— B _t) =	179,71	
		P Value right tailed (SINE) =	0,00238964	
PROPORTIONS.				
		(a/N) × 100 = (1347 / 247318) × 100 =	0,54 %	
		(b/N) × 100 = (154216 / 247318) × 100 =	62,36 %	
		(c/N) × 100 = (590 / 247318) × 100 =	0,24 %	
		(d/N) × 100 = (91165 / 247318) × 100 =	36,86 %	
		(a/A) × 100 = (1347 / 155563) × 100 =	0,87 %	
		(b/A) × 100 = (154216 / 155563) × 100 =	99,13 %	
		(c/ not A) × 100 = (590 / 91755) × 100 =	0,64 %	
		(d/ not A) × 100 = (91165 / 91755) × 100 =	99,36 %	
		(a/B) × 100 = (1347 / 1937) × 100 =	69,54 %	
		(c/B) × 100 = (590 / 1937) × 100 =	30,46 %	
		(b/ not B) × 100 = (154216 / 245381) × 100 =	62,85 %	
		(d/ not B) × 100 = (91165 / 245381) × 100 =	37,15 %	
		(A/N) × 100 = (155563 / 247318) × 100 =	62,90 %	
		(not A/N) × 100 = (91755 / 247318) × 100 =	37,10 %	
		(B/N) × 100 = (1937 / 247318) × 100 =	0,78 %	
		(not B/N) × 100 = (245381 / 247318) × 100 =	99,22 %	
ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.				
RELATIVE RISK (RR).				
		RR (necessary condition) =	1,34660125	
		RR (sufficient condition) =	1,10649504	
OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.				
		Odds ratio (OR) =	1,34962864	
		Index of relationship (IOR) =	0,10557292	
STUDY DESIGN.				
		p(IOU)=	0,36316807	
		p(IOI)=	0,62116789	

³⁰Geris JM, Spector LG, Pfeiffer RM, Limaye AP, Yu KJ, Engels EA. Cancer risk associated with cytomegalovirus infection among solid organ transplant recipients in the United States. *Cancer*. 2022 Nov 15;128(22):3985-3994. doi: 10.1002/encr.34462. Epub 2022 Sep 20. PMID: 36126024; PMCID: PMC9633408.

Due to the unavailability of CMV IgG serostatus data for most transplant recipients before the year 2000, the analysis was restricted to transplants conducted from 2000 onward. This restriction ensured the reliability of serostatus-based groupings and minimized data inconsistencies. Geris et al. reported that 62.9%, or 155,563 recipients, in the cohort of 247,318 solid organ transplant recipients were CMV IgG seropositive prior to transplantation.

Within this cohort, there were 1,932 cases of lung cancer. Notably, 1,937 pretransplant lung cancer cases were CMV-positive. It must be emphasized that

$$1,937 - 1,932 = 590$$

pretransplant lung cancer cases were CMV-negative.

If CMV positivity were to be considered a necessary condition for the development of lung cancer, this finding would be particularly difficult to reconcile.

If the 590 cases were assumed to have arisen due to errors, several potential sources of such errors could be considered in detail:

1. Sensitivity and Specificity of the IgG Kit:

The diagnostic kit used to determine CMV IgG serostatus may have limited sensitivity or specificity, leading to false-negative results in some individuals who were actually CMV-positive.

2. Sample Handling and Storage:

Errors in the handling, storage, or transportation of blood samples could degrade the quality of specimens, resulting in inaccurate serological test results.

3. Data Entry and Transmission Errors:

Mistakes during data recording or transferring information between laboratories and the registry could lead to mismatches between test results and patient records.

4. Temporal Variability in CMV Status:

CMV IgG levels may fluctuate, and individuals who were CMV-negative at the time of testing could have converted to seropositive status later, before lung cancer developed.

5. Unrecorded Clinical History:

A subset of individuals might have had prior CMV exposure or reactivation episodes that were not captured or reported in the study data, leading to misclassification of their CMV status.

These considerations emphasize the critical need for robust methodological and procedural safeguards to minimize inaccuracies in such studies. Additionally, this overview of potential errors highlights the importance of acknowledging and accounting for uncertainty in decision-making. It under-

scores the necessity of explicitly reporting the significance level (α) and the corresponding P -value as integral components of justifying the inferences drawn.

2.2. Methods

The statistical methods³¹ employed in the analysis were designed to rigorously assess the data and address the study's objectives. A significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ was applied, ensuring that the probability of Type I errors (false positives) remained within acceptable bounds. Hypothesis testing was conducted using a one-sided approach, reflecting the directional nature of the research question.

Innovative statistical methods (see Barukčić, 2021) were introduced to evaluate causal relationships, particularly focusing on whether CMV positivity constituted a necessary condition for the development of lung cancer. Proportional analyses were employed to compare the prevalence of CMV IgG seropositivity across groups with and without lung cancer.

Advanced techniques were utilized to estimate the strength and significance of associations, incorporating causal inference frameworks to move beyond simple correlation. These methods also allowed for the testing of necessary conditions, determining whether the absence of CMV positivity could reliably exclude the occurrence of lung cancer. The analysis further leveraged new computational tools to assess the robustness of these findings under varying assumptions and to account for potential biases.

This multifaceted approach ensured a comprehensive evaluation of the data, providing nuanced insights into the potential relationship between CMV and lung cancer.

³¹Ilija Barukčić. The causal relationship k. MATEC Web Conf., 336 (2021) 09032. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1051/mateconf/202133609032>

3. Results

The one-sided right-tailed hypothesis test evaluates whether the theoretical probability π_0 is greater than the observed value p .

Our Hypotheses for a Right-Tailed Test:

- $H_0 : \pi_0 \leq (p = 0.99761441)$
The null hypothesis states that the theoretical probability π_0 is less than or equal to the observed probability p .
- $H_A : \pi_0 > (p = 0.99761441)$
The alternative hypothesis states that the theoretical probability π_0 is greater than the observed probability p .

The observed p is given as:

$$p(\text{CMV} \leftarrow \text{Lung cancer}) = \frac{1347 + 245381}{247318} = 1 - \frac{590}{247318} = 0.9976144074 \quad (1)$$

The one-sided right-tailed P Value is calculated (see Barukčić, 2024, pp. 286–291) as.

$$\text{P value}_{\text{one sided right tailed}} = 1 - p(\text{CMV} \leftarrow \text{Lung cancer}) + \frac{1}{n} = \frac{590}{247318} + \frac{1}{247318} = 0.002389636015 \quad (2)$$

The decision rules can be summarized as follows:

Test Type	$p\text{Value} < \alpha$	$p\text{Value} \geq \alpha$
Left-Tailed Test	H_A accepted	H_0 accepted
Right-Tailed Test	H_A accepted	H_0 accepted

The P -value is less than α , so we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis:

$$H_A : \pi_0 > 0.9976 \quad (\text{with } p = 0.9976).$$

In other words, the necessary condition relationship between CMV and lung cancer in the population is:

$$H_A : \pi_0 > 0.9976, \quad \text{P-value} = 0.002389636015.$$

Therefore, we conclude that without human CMV infection, no human lung cancer, as indicated by the significant P -value of 0.002389636015.

4. Discussion

In this study, we have been able to establish a necessary condition relationship between CMV infection and lung cancer. **Without** human CMV infection, **no** human lung cancer, supported by a significant *P*-value of 0.00239. However, it is crucial to be cautious when drawing conclusions from data that may inadequately represent reality due to various sources of error. The relationship between CMV and lung cancer remains complex, and although the necessary relationship between CMV and lung cancer appears strong—suggesting a potential prerequisite for causality—this finding does not necessarily imply direct causation. There is always a risk of erroneously inferring causation from insufficient data, especially in observational studies where confounding factors could influence the results. This is precisely why we must report measures like the *P*-value.

Furthermore, while the *P*-value suggests statistical significance, this alone does not guarantee the practical or clinical significance of the relationship. Statistical significance can sometimes result from large sample sizes or rare events, and care should be taken to interpret the magnitude of the effect. Therefore, future studies should aim to replicate these findings in different populations and contexts to confirm whether CMV infection is indeed a necessary condition for the development of lung cancer.

In addition, other research techniques, such as longitudinal studies, randomized controlled trials et cetera are required to better understand the temporal dynamics and mechanistic pathways between CMV and lung cancer. These studies should aim to rule out potential biases, explore the role of other viruses or environmental factors, and refine the methods used to assess causality.

5. Conclusion

Despite the contradictions and the complexities involved, we have gathered a certain degree of evidence that CMV infection is a necessary condition for the development of human lung cancer.

‘**Without** human CMV infection, **no** human lung cancer (*P* – value = 0.00239). ’

However, further research is necessary to confirm this potential link and understand its underlying mechanisms.

Acknowledgments

No funding or any financial support by a third party was received.

Erratum

Unfortunately, some misprints appeared in the previous publications, especially in the section of definitions. Some of the misprints have been brought up to date in this publication as far as possible.

Private note

The definition section of a paper need not and does not necessarily contain new scientific aspects. Above all, it also serves to better understand a scientific publication, to follow every step of the arguments of an author and to explain in greater details the fundamentals on which a publication is based. Therefore, there is no objective need to force authors to reinvent a scientific wheel once and again unless such a need appears obviously factually necessary. The effort to write about a certain subject in an original way in multiple publications does not exclude the necessity simply to cut and paste from an earlier work, and has nothing to do with self-plagiarism. However, such an attitude cannot simply be transferred to the sections' introduction, results, discussion and conclusions et cetera.

Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are frequently used:

CMV	Cytomegalovirus
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
EBV	Epstein-Bar virus
IHC	Immunohistochemistry
ISH	In situ hybridization
PCR	Polymerase chain reaction
BMI	body mass index
ESRD	end-stage renal disease
HD	hemodialysis
CABG	coronary artery bypass graft
CCI	Charlson comorbidity index
AMI	acute myocardial infarction
MACE	major adverse cardiovascular events
LDL-C	low-density lipoprotein cholesterol
GFR	glomerular filtration rate
STEMI	ST elevation myocardial infarction
NSTEMI	non-ST elevation myocardial infarction
MI	myocardial infarction
ARB	angiotensin receptor blocker
ACEI	angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors
CCBs	calcium channel blockers
IOR	index of relationship
p(IOU)	index of unfairness
p(IOI)	index of independence
k	Causal relationship
SINE	Necessary condition relationship
IMP	Sufficient condition relationship
EXCL	exclusion relationship
RR	Relative risk
RR (nc)	relative risk (necessary condition)
RR (sc)	relative risk (sufficient condition)
OR	Odds ratio
P Value	Probability of significance

References

- Ilija Barukčić. *Theoriae causalitatis principia mathematica*. Books On Demand, Norderstedt, Germany, 2024. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14544457. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14544457>.
- Ilija Barukčić. The causal relationship k. *MATEC Web of Conferences*, 336:09032, 2021. ISSN 2261-236X. doi: 10.1051/mateconf/202133609032. CSCNS2020. Web of Science. Free full text: EDP Sciences.
- J. M. Geris, L. G. Spector, R. M. Pfeiffer, A. P. Limaye, K. J. Yu, and E. A. Engels. Cancer risk associated with cytomegalovirus infection among solid organ transplant recipients in the united states. *Cancer*, 128(22):3985–3994, Nov 2022. doi: 10.1002/cncr.34462. URL <https://doi.org/10.1002/cncr.34462>. Epub 2022 Sep 20.
- Ernest W Goodpasture and Fritz B Talbot. Concerning the nature of protozoan-like cells in certain lesions of infancy. *American Journal of Diseases of Children*, 21(5):415–425, 1921.
- H Ribbert. Über protozoenartige zellen in der niere eines syphilitischen neugeborenen und in der parotis von kindern. *Zentralblatt für allgemeine Pathologie und pathologische Anatomie*, 15:945–948, 1904.
- Margaret G Smith. Propagation in tissue cultures of a cytopathogenic virus from human salivary gland virus (sgv) disease. *Proceedings of the Society for Experimental Biology and Medicine*, 92(2):424–430, 1956.
- Margaret G Smith and Frank Vellios. Inclusion disease or generalized salivary gland virus infection. *American Medical Association - Archives of pathology*, 50(6):862–84, 1950.
- P Row Wallace, W Hartley Janet, Waterman Samuel, C Turner Horace, and J Huebner Robert. Cytopathogenic agent resembling human salivary gland virus recovered from tissue cultures of human adenoids. *Proceedings of the Society for Experimental Biology and Medicine*, 92(2):418–424, 1956.
- Thomas H Weller, James B Hanshaw, DE Scott, et al. Serologic differentiation of viruses responsible for cytomegalic inclusion disease. *Virology*, 12(1):130–32, 1960.
- Thos H Weller, JC Macauley, JM Craig, and P Wirth. Isolation of intranuclear inclusion producing agents from infants with illnesses resembling cytomegalic inclusion disease. *Proceedings of the Society for Experimental Biology and Medicine*, 94(1):4–12, 1957.

Associated Data**Copyright**

Copyright © December 29, 2024 by Ilija Barukčić, Horandstrasse, Jever, Germany. All Rights Reserved. Alle Rechte vorbehalten.

© 2025 Ilija Barukčić^{a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i, j, k, l, m} Ilija Barukčić, Chief-Editor, Jever, Germany, December 29, 2024. All rights reserved. Alle Rechte vorbehalten. This is an open access article which can be downloaded under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>).

I was born October, 1st 1961 in Novo Selo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, former Yugoslavia. I am of Croatian origin. From 1982-1989 C.E., I studied human medicine at the University of Hamburg, Germany. Meanwhile, I am working as a specialist of internal medicine. My basic field of research since my high school days at the Wirtschaftsgymnasium Bruchsal, Baden Württemberg, Germany is the mathematization of the relationship between a cause and an effect valid without any restriction under any circumstances including the conditions of classical logic, probability theory, quantum mechanics, special and general theory of relativity, human medicine et cetera. I endeavour to investigate positions of quantum mechanics, relativity theory, mathematics et cetera, only insofar as these positions put into question or endanger **the general validity of the principle of causality.**

^a<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6988-2780>

^b<https://www.webofscience.com/wos/author/record/1972920>

^c<https://www.scopus.com/authid/detail.uri?authorId=37099674500>

^d<https://www.scopus.com/authid/detail.uri?authorId=54974181600>

^e<https://www.mendeley.com/search/?authorFullName=Ilija%20Baruk%C4%8Di%C4%87&page=1&query=Barukcic&sortBy=relevance>

^f<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Ilija-Barukcic-2>

^g<https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=keywords:%22Baruk%C4%8Di%C4%87%22&sort=mostviewed>

^h<https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=keywords:%22Baruk%C4%8Di%C4%87,%20Conference%22>

ⁱ<https://twitter.com/ilijabarukcic?lang=de>

^jhttps://twitter.com/Causation_Journ

^khttps://vixra.org/author/ilija_barukcic

^l<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCwf3w1IngcukIO0jpw8HTwg>

^m<https://portal.dnb.de/opac/showNextResultSite?currentResultId=%22Barukcic%22%26any¤tPosition=30>

^m<https://portal.dnb.de/opac/showNextResultSite?currentResultId=%22Barukcic%22%26any¤tPosition=30>